

**STUDY OF MIGRATION PROCESSES AND MATERIAL CULTURE
OF THE BRONZE AGE**

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Abstract. Today, the Bronze Age material cultural monuments are considered to be a community that developed crafts along with agriculture and animal husbandry, and they have achieved great success in the field of jewelry, which is a branch of crafts. The study of their migration processes, historical and archaeological data have been scientifically analyzed.

Keywords: steppe pastoralists, Aryan problem, Indo-Iranian tribes, enterprising and entrepreneurial class, Eurasia, Altai, Yenisei.

Introduction. At the end of the 3rd millennium BC and the 2nd millennium BC, the communities of the ancient farming world of Namozgoh V, VI and Sopolli cultures in the southern regions of Central Asia were experiencing a period of high urbanization development typical of the ancient Eastern civilization, in the central regions - the Zarafshan Valley, on the one hand, local domesticated livestock and motiga farming communities - the Zamonbabo culture, on the other hand, the Sarazm culture that migrated to the valley from the south, in the north-east of Central Asia, the snake totem and the famous Haq treasure in the ancient Fergana regions, and in the north-western regions of the region - the Suyorgan and Tozabogyob cultures in ancient Khorezm were experiencing a period of ethnocultural upsurge.

History of study. The problem of the boundaries of the territorial settlement of the ancient peoples of Central Asia, mentioned in the first written sources since the second half of the 19th century, has become a topical topic in the works of orientalists (E. Zakhau, V. Geiger, V. Tomashek). This issue was considered at the beginning of the 20th century (I. Markvart, A. Hermann) and, taking into account archaeological data, was put forward in subsequent years (MM Dyakonov, VM Masson, BY Stavisky). This problem was especially addressed in the works of a number of researchers (IV Pyankov, P. Bernard, GP Frankfort, EV Rtveladze, JK Garden, etc.) in the 70s and 80s of the last century. The historiography of the topic was sufficiently covered by IV Pyankov. The researcher's work focused on the analysis of Greco-Roman sources on the history and historical geography of Bactria, as well as the ideas of ancient authors about the territorial borders of Sogd and Bactria, which passed

through mountains and rivers [1].

As a result of extensive archaeological research carried out in Central Asia in the 1970s and 1980s, existing scientific views on the historical geography of this region have fundamentally changed.

Among the issues considered at the 1977 International Symposium on the History of Ethnic Problems of Central Asia, the idea that the 2nd millennium BC was an important stage in the ethnogenesis of the peoples of the region and, in particular, that the foundation for the formation of modern peoples was laid during this period was first put forward [2]. The reports of the conference participants considered the issues of the spread of Indo-Iranian tribes, the linguistic (linguistics), archaeological and historical-cultural aspects of the “Aryan problem” associated with the migration of steppe herders of the Andronovo culture to Central Asia in the Bronze Age. According to other alternative views , the homeland of the Indo-Iranians is located in Old Asia. Academician A. Askarov, speaking specifically about the origin of the Aryans, comes to the following conclusion: “The Aryans were a social product of the nomadic stage of life in the economic rise of the pastoral tribes, their enterprising and entrepreneurial layer, the noble class of the emerging primitive class society ” [3].

In the 1990s and early 2000s, the work of researchers such as AA Askarov, EV Rtveldze, AS Sagdullayev, T.Sh. Shirinov, Sh.B. Shaydullayev, and NA Avanesova was of great importance in illuminating the history of the Bronze Age [3]. New information was used to solve various scientific problems.

It is also worth noting the dissertations of such researchers as T.Sh. Shirinov, Sh.B. Shaydullayev, M.X. Esanov, D.O. Karimova, A.Sh. Shaydullayev, J.E. Togayev, and T.H. Norkobilov [4].

The results of new research are also reflected in co-authored monographs [5]. Their content includes information on the geography and cartography of Bronze Age monuments.

of great importance in this regard are the scientific works of foreign specialists such as K. Lamberg-Karlovsky, F. Koll, F. Hiebert, D. Huff, N. Boroffka, J. Chierry , and J. Lutz [12-13-14].

The main part. During this period, Bronze Age tribal communities, known as Andronovs, were widespread in the Asian part of the Eurasian steppes. Their most widespread areas were the southeastern Urals, the entire steppes of Kazakhstan, the Altai Mountains, the Yenisei basins, the Yettisuv and Balkhash basins in the south, and the southern Siberian regions in general. Their economy was based on animal husbandry and mining - metallurgy. There are many points of view and various

hypotheses in science about their origin , and experts have not yet come to a final conclusion, a consensus.

If we approach the issue logically, the communities of the Andronovo culture did not come to the regions of South Siberia, to the Eurasian steppes from somewhere, but rather were formed as a product of inter-tribal economic and ethnocultural ties on the basis of local Eneolithic and Early Bronze Age monuments. Therefore, we believe that the historical roots of the tribes of the Andronovo culture should be sought precisely in these territories, among the local Eneolithic and Early Bronze Age tribal communities . Because the factual materials related to the formation of the Novokumak and Petrov complexes as the first stage of the Andronovo culture also require the same conclusion.

At the same time, it is worth noting that , judging by the results of extensive research conducted over many years to find a solution to the problems associated with the formation of the Andronovo culture, even searching for a specific point of origin for its historical roots does not yield any results. Therefore, it can be concluded that the Andronovo culture is an ethnocultural unity formed on the basis of a mixture of ethnos and traditions of the late Neolithic and Eneolithic periods in a wide historical geographical area (the territories of the South-Eastern Urals and Northern Kazakhstan) . This is a hypothesis close to historical truth. A similar idea was also expressed in due time by the archaeologist AI Martinov, namely, that the formation of the Andronovo culture is associated with fundamental changes that occurred in the economy of the Bronze Age cattle-breeding tribes on a wide territorial scale¹.

What were these changes, what factors underlie them? Natural geographical conditions, socio-economic factors, underground and above-ground natural resources, the ascetic lifestyle of steppe herders? Perhaps all of them led to the fundamental socio-economic changes that occurred during the Bronze Age.

Indeed, the Eurasian steppes of the Eneolithic and Bronze Ages, due to their unique natural-geographical climatic conditions and ecological features, have wide opportunities for the development of the livestock sector of primitive agriculture. Already in the Neolithic period, domestic livestock farming in the life of the population of this region was inextricably linked with the farming of the nomadic tribes. This ensured the transition of the Andronov tribes to a sedentary lifestyle. The development of primitive agriculture on this basis freed the clan communities of the Neolithic period from the traditional exploitative economy and led to the development of the livestock sector of the sedentary primitive life, which was formed in accordance with the natural conditions of the region.

In the east of the Eurasian steppe, that is, in its Asian part, first of all, in the South-Eastern Urals, that is, within the territory of the present Chelyabinsk region and Northern Kazakhstan, a gradual transition from domestic cattle breeding to pasture cattle breeding begins. It is not unlikely that these processes occurred approximately in the Eneolithic and Early Bronze Ages. It is precisely in this zone that there were appropriate natural opportunities and factors for the early development of pasture cattle breeding.

Conclusion. Thus, the socio-economic and ethnocultural fundamental changes that occurred in the Eurasian steppes in the 2nd millennium BC led to the transition from pastoralism to nomadic pastoralism. This led to the formation of a permanent wintering center for pastoralists of the Eurasian regions. This wintering center for Bronze Age pastoralists was the South-Eastern Urals, where the moderate natural and geographical climatic conditions of this place, warm water resources suitable for wintering due to the formation of the Ural River, and the underground mineral wealth of these places, on the one hand, created wide opportunities for the development of the mining industry and the organization of production related to metallurgical deposits, and on the other hand, on their basis, led to the centralization of the ideological foundations of the social and economic, ethnocultural and political life of pastoralist communities in these places.

List of used literature:

1. Pyankov I.V. Bactria and antique tradition (obshchie dannye o strane: nazvanie i territoriya). - Dushanbe: Donish, 1982. - 62 p.
2. Askarov A.A., Shirinov T.Sh. Ranyaya gorodskaya kultura epoxi bronzy yuga Sredney Azii. - Samarkand: IA AN RUz, 1993. - 162 p.
3. Askarov A. The problem of the Aryans: new views and approaches. "The history of Uzbekistan in material culture and written sources". –Tashkent, 2005. –P. 71–72.
4. Askarov AA The main features of the ancient world of Central Asia // Social Sciences in Uzbekistan, 1994. – No. 6. – P. 31-35.
5. Shaidullaev Sh.B. Severnaya Bactria and the epoch of early days. - Tashkent, 2000. - 126 p.
6. Rtveladze E.V. Tsivilizatsii, gosudarstva, kulturey Tsentralnoy Azii. - Tashkent, 2005. - 288 p.
7. Avanesova N.A. Proyavlenie stepnyx traditsiy v Sapalinskoy kulture // Tsivilizatsii i kulturey Tsentralnoy Azii v edinstve i mnogoobrazii. - Tashkent, 2010. - S. 107-133.

8. Shirinov T.Sh. Ranyaya gorodskaya kultura epoxi bronzy yuga Sredney Azii: Autoref. diss. ... Dr. desire science - M.: Institute of Archeology RAN, 1993. - 49 p.
9. Esanov M.Kh. Reflection of the Avestan society in archaeological materials (in the example of the bronze age material culture monuments of Ancient Bactria and Margyona): History science. name diss. ... autoref. – Samarkand: Institute of Archeology of the Russian Federation, 2007. – 29 p.
10. Shaydullaev Sh.B. Stages of the emergence and development of statehood in the territory of Uzbekistan (on the example of Bactria): Doctor of History. Dissertation ... author's ref. – Samarkand: Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, 2009. – 50 p.
11. Karimova D.O. Burial rites and religious beliefs of the population of Northern Bactria (on the example of monuments of material culture of the Bronze Age): Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in History. ... author's abstract. – Tashkent: UzMU, 2017. – 21 p.
12. Shaydullaev A.Sh. Glyptics and sphragistics of the Sopolli culture.: Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in History. ... author's abstract. – Samarkand: Institute of Archaeology of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, 2018. – 18 p.;
13. Lamberg-Korlovsky CC The Bronze Age of Bactria // Ba s tria. An Ancient Oasis Civilizations . Rome-Venezia, 1989. – Pp. 17-32.
14. Kohl's Ph.L. Central Asia. Palaeolithic Beginnings to the Early Iron Age. - Paris, 1984. - R p. 310 ; Hiebert FT Origins of the Bronze Age Oasis Civilization in Central Asia // American School of Prehistori s Research Bulletin. Vol. 42. - Cambridge, 1994. - Pp. 89-95.
15. Huff D. Djarkutan Archaeological Research on Tepe VI // IMKU . Vyp . 31. - Samarkand , 2000. - S. 58-69; Boroffka N., Cierry J., Lutz J. Bronze Age tin from Central Asia // Late Prehistoric of the Eurasian Steppe. - Cambridge, 1999. - Pp. 14-29.